

Some Azido and Cyanato Complexes of Bivalent Metals Containing Bipyridyl and *o*-Phenanthroline

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Manuscript received 26 March 1976 ; revised 6 July 1977 ; accepted 3 October 1977

Mixed ligand complexes of formulae $[MLX_n]_n nH_2O$, where $M=Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II)$ and $Hg(II)$, $L=oo'$ -bipyridyl and *o*-phenanthroline and $X=N_3^-$ and NCO^- have been isolated and characterised by analyses, molar conductance, magnetic moment, infra-red and electronic spectral data. The azido complexes of $Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II)$ and $Cu(II)$ have octahedral geometry with azide bridges through a single nitrogen atom. All other compounds have tetrahedral geometry with terminal nitrogen bonded anionic ligands.

AZIDE and cyanate are peculiar anionic ligands with high electron charge density over the nitrogen atoms, which makes a metal bind to the ligand either terminally through the nitrogen atom or in a bridged manner¹. We report in this paper our studies on the azido and cyanato complexes of some bivalent metal ions containing two common diamine ligands viz. *oo'*-bipyridyl and *o*-phenanthroline ($MLX_n \cdot nH_2O$ type, where L =diamine and X =anionic ligand).

Materials and Methods

All chemicals used were of pure grade and solvents were used after distillation.

1 m. mole of metal chloride or nitrate was dissolved in ~2 ml. of water and was treated with slight excess of the diamine in ~5 ml. of alcohol. The solution was warmed and to it stoichiometric amount of dilute aqueous solution of sodium azide or potassium cyanate was added. The mixture was refluxed for 30 minutes to ensure completion of reaction. The precipitated complex was filtered and recrystallised from DMSO and vacuum.dried.

Magnetic moments were measured from solid specimens using Gouy method. Molar conductance, UV and visible spectra were measured from DMSO/methanol solutions. Infra-red spectra were recorded in the range 4000-650 cm^{-1} in KBr discs.

Results and Discussion

Table I gives the analytical, melting point and magnetic moment data along with characteristic infra-red absorption band positions of the anionic ligands after complexation.

All the compounds are non-electrolytes having very low molar conductance values.

Azido complexes—All the compounds (excepting $Cd(II)$ and $Zn(II)$ complexes) have magnetic

moments fairly within the normal range of spin-free octahedral complexes, although the magnetic moments of only $Co(II)$ and $Ni(II)$ complexes are diagnostic of their structures.

The charge-transfer absorptions may be divided into three categories. The first set of bands belonging to intra-ligand $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ origin²⁻⁴ occur at 47,620-45,450 cm^{-1} ; 44,250-40,320 cm^{-1} and 37,665-33,220 cm^{-1} . The second category (34,480-32,360 cm^{-1})²⁻⁴ is possibly due to ligand-metal charge-transfer. The third band (26,670-23,470 cm^{-1}) occurs often as a split band and possibly arises out of $e_g \rightarrow \pi^*$, metal-ligand charge-transfer²⁻⁴.

The ligand field bands of $Cu(II)$ complexes appear as a broad band having the centre of gravity at 14,925 cm^{-1} (*oo'*-bipyridyl) and 15,210 cm^{-1} (*o*-phenanthroline), at the same positions and intensities reported by Dutta and De⁵. The positions, intensities and shapes of the absorption bands are diagnostic of a distorted octahedral structure with CuN_6 chromophore⁶. Using Billing and Underhill's procedure⁷, the 10 Dq values have been calculated to be 7,462 and 7,610 cm^{-1} for bipyridyl and *o*-phenanthroline complexes respectively.

The only ligand field bands observed in case of nickel(II) complexes are at 17,500 cm^{-1} and 16,810 cm^{-1} respectively, owing to the transition ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2 transition). The positions and intensities of the bands, associated with the μ_{eff} values (3.28 and 2.90 BM respectively) clearly indicate octahedral symmetry with the complexes^{6,9}. The ν_2 band appears to have been obscured by the intense $M \rightarrow L$ charge transfer bands and the spectra have not been recorded over the range to get the ν_1 band. A band at 15,500 cm^{-1} observed in $Ni(bp.)_2(N_3)_2$ is perhaps due to a spin-forbidden transition.

$Co(II)$ complexes give clear ligand field bands⁹ ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1) at 7,565 and 7,690 cm^{-1} ,

TABLE-1

COLOUR, ANALYSES, MAGNETIC MOMENT AND INFRA-RED SPECTRAL DATA OF AZIDO AND CYANATO COMPLEXES

Compounds	Colour ^a	Melting point (°C)	Analyses data ^b		μ_{eff} (B.M.)	Infra-red spectral bands.(cm ⁻¹) ^c		
			%M.	%N.		ν_s	ν_{as}	$\nu_s + \nu_{as}$
Mn(bp)(N ₃) ₂	Light yellow	281	18.4 (18.61)	32.9 (33.23)	5.90	1315 sh	2098 vs } 2060 sh }	3330 w
Co(bp)(N ₃) ₂	Brick red	288	19.8 (19.70)	32.8 (32.78)	4.70	1315 s	2095 vs } 2047 sh }	3350 w, br
Ni(bp)(N ₃) ₂	Green	234	19.8 (19.64)	32.8 (32.81)	3.28	1300 m	2090 vs } 2050 sh }	
Cu(bp)(N ₃) ₂	Yellowish green	224	20.7 (20.55)	32.0 (32.29)	1.84	1315 m	2060 vs, br	
Cd(bp)(N ₃) ₂	White	288	31.8 (31.88)	27.8 (27.81)	—	1285 s	2070 vs	3340 w
Hg(bp)(N ₃) ₂	White	220	45.6 (45.50)	22.1 (22.25)	—	1315 s	2035 vs	
Mn(o-phen)(N ₃) ₂	Pale yellow	280	17.9 (17.41)	30.5 (30.73)	5.85	1280 m	2090 sh } 2050 vs }	3250 w, br
Co(o-phen)(N ₃) ₂	Brick red	>300	18.2 (18.23)	30.1 (30.35)	4.66	1290 m	2060 vs } 2035 sh }	3220 w, br
Ni(o-phen)(N ₃) ₂	Green	255	18.2 (18.16)	30.1 (30.37)	2.90	1300 m	2075 vs } 2050 sh }	3300 w, br
Cu(o-phen)(N ₃) ₂	Green	269	19.7 (19.40)	29.8 (29.92)	1.87	1287 m	2055 vs } 2040 sh }	3250 w, br
Cd(o-phen)(N ₃) ₂	White	213	30.9 (29.84)	26.0 (26.04)	—	1285 m	2050 vs	3300 w, br
Mn(bp)(NCO) ₂ · 6H ₂ O	Light brown	280	13.7 (13.63)	13.7 (13.90)	5.88	—	2180 vbr	
Ni(bp)(NCO) ₂ · H ₂ O	Green	254	18.5 (18.52)	17.6 (17.68)	3.78	—	2160 sh } 2215 s }	
Cu(bp)(NCO) ₂	Blue	186	20.7 (20.55)	18.6 (18.76)	2.10	—	2180 vbr	
Cd(bp)(NCO) ₂	White	292	31.5 (31.88)	15.8 (15.89)	—	—	2205 s, br	
Mn(o-phen)(NCO) ₂ · 3H ₂ O	Pale yellow	275	14.7 (14.70)	14.8 (15.02)	5.40	—	2160 s } 2210 s }	
Co(o-phen)(NCO) ₂	Deep blue	204	17.9 (18.23)	17.3 (17.34)	4.82	—	2180 s } 2200 sh }	
Ni(o-phen)(NCO) ₂ · 3H ₂ O	Green	261	15.5 (15.57)	14.7 (14.86)	4.16	—	2180 vs, br	
Cu(o-phen)(NCO) ₂	Blue	201	19.3 (19.40)	16.8 (17.10)	2.12	—	2165 s } 2210 s }	
Cd(o-phen)(NCO) ₂	White	266	30.2 (29.54)	14.7 (14.88)	—	—	2165 sh } 2215 s }	

^a. All compounds are either crystalline or micro-crystalline.

^b. The values in parenthesis are theoretical values.

^c. The ν_s , ν_{as} and combination bands correspond to azide and cyanate group vibrations.

⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴A_{2g}(F) (ν_3) at 15,870 and 15,380 cm⁻¹, and ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴T_{1g}(P) (ν_3) at 19,530 and 19,720 cm⁻¹ respectively for bipyridyl and o-phenanthroline complexes. The ν_2/ν_1 ratio⁹ (~2.05), 10Dq value⁹ (8,305 and 7,690 cm⁻¹), μ_{eff} .⁸ (4.70 and 4.66 B.M) indicate the complexes to be octahedral.

Mn(II) complexes gave very weak ligand field bands which could not be detected clearly, because of their very low solubility.

The infra-red spectra of the compounds contain modified bands of the amines and azide groups indicating their co-ordination. The ν_{as} , (N₃⁻) and ν_s (N₃⁻) bands of azide generally appear at ~2,100 and ~1,300 cm⁻¹ respectively¹⁰⁻¹³. A very weak band also appears at ~3,400 cm⁻¹ for a $\nu_{as} + \nu_s$ combination.¹³ Nelson et al.¹² and Ziola et al.¹⁴ have shown that in a symmetric bridged structure

ν_s is either i.r. inactive or very weak unlike the case of cyanates¹², whereas i.r. active band at ~1,300 cm⁻¹ is diagnostic of terminal and single atom bridged structures. Since such type of i.r. spectra are observed for Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) complexes and they are all suggested to be octahedral from electronic spectra and magnetic moment data, the azide must obviously be having a single atom bridged type structure. Cd(II) and Hg(II) have difference in the ν_{as} (N₃⁻) as single bands unlike the split one in the others. The azide ion may be linked terminally and the compounds may be of tetrahedral type as is generally the case with Cd(II) and Hg(II) complexes.

Cyanato complexes—The magnetic moments of the compounds are well within the range prescribed for tetrahedral complexes.

The charge transfer transitions occur as three distinct bands. In the case of bipyridyl complexes an additional weak shoulder appears at $\sim 46,500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ to the band at $\sim 40,000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. In the case of all the *o*-phenanthroline compounds and Cd(bp)(NCO)₂ they merge into a single band. As assigned in the corresponding azido complexes, the above bands together with the band at $37,665\text{-}33,555 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ belong to the intra-ligand $\pi\text{-}\pi^*$ origin. The second category of bands fall into the region $34,720\text{-}32,360 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, possibly due to ligand $\rightarrow$ metal charge transfer. The third category of bands are not observed; possibly they move to higher energy and get enveloped by the intense higher energy bands.

A single broad band in the ligand field region occur at $13,700$ and $14,050 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for bipyridyl and *o*-phenanthroline complexes of Cu(II) respectively, for the ${}^3T_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3E_{2g}$ transition. The Co(II) complexes show the ligand field bands in two closely spaced groups. The first group correspond to ${}^4A_g \rightarrow {}^4T_1(F)$ transition (ν_3 , $6,900$ and $7,700 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) occurring at the same positions for both the diamine(L) complexes. The second group (ν_3) corresponding to ${}^4A_g \rightarrow {}^4T_1(P)$ transition occur at $15,800$; $16,420$; $17,420$ and $15,750$; $16,450$; $17,390 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for Co(bp)(NCO)₂ and Co(*o*-phen)(NCO)₂ complexes respectively. The general pattern of bands of Cu(II) and Co(II) complexes correspond to tetrahedral structure^{8,9}. Supporting evidence to this may be obtained from the magnetic moment for Cu(II) ($\mu_{\text{eff.}} > 2 \text{ B.M.}$)⁸ and Co(II) ($\mu_{\text{eff.}} 4.4\text{-}4.8 \text{ B.M.}$)⁸.

Ni(II) exhibits weak bands at $15,380$ ($\epsilon 60$); $13,160$ ($\epsilon 31$); $9,610$ ($\epsilon 34$) and $17,860$ ($\epsilon 36$); $12,820$ ($\epsilon 26$); $8,330$ ($\epsilon 13$) cm^{-1} for both bipyridyl and *o*-phenanthroline complexes respectively. The band positions and intensities are more or less similar to those of octahedral complexes. Since the magnetic moment data, in the solid state, clearly point to tetrahedral structure, it is assumed that Ni(II) complexes probably enter into solvation during solution. There is an observed weakening of colour in solution. However, our attempts to isolate the adduct for complete characterisation failed.

Mn(II) complexes have very weak absorptions in the ligand field region to record. In analogy with other cyanato complexes, they are also assumed to be tetrahedral.

The infra-red spectra, besides containing modified bands of amines contain the vibrations of the cyanato group. Although ν_{as} vibration poorly characterise the bonding of the cyanato group, a diagonalistic result may be obtained from the $\nu_s(\text{NCO}^-)$ vibration^{12,15-17}. The $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{NCO}^-)$ is observed as a doublet centering around $2,200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, whereas the region $1,380\text{-}1,200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is completely transparent excepting a modified vibration of the hetero ligand. It suggests a terminal N-bonded cyanato group.^{12,15-17}

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to the Sambalpur University for financial support and to RSIC, Madras for their help in recording some spectra.

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